

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRODUCTS WITH PERSONALITY AND CO-CREATED PRODUCTS

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Abstract: The purpose of this paper is to assess the importance of co-created products and products with personality and people's reaction to them. In a world in which people want to stand out and be unique, this kind of products gain increasing importance by eliciting emotions and pleasant feelings. Thus, strong bonds are created between users and these types of products, and some of them end up being preserved long after they are unable to fulfil their primary functions. Products with personality and co-created products will become the future of design, because people have a growing desire to be surprised and intrigued.

Keywords: product with personality, co-created products, design, emotions,

Introduction

The first contact between man and object – which is predominantly visual - sets the tone of his experience with the product design. Man reacts emotionally to everything around him, without necessarily interacting with people - tending to develop thoughts and emotions. We attribute human characteristics, states and feelings to things in our environment such as objects, plants, and animals.

Norbert Bolz describes how the emotional design strategy is used to endow objects with the illusion of depth and feeling. A designer aims at aesthetically modeling the product by integrating state-of-the-art technology in an intuitive way, and putting the user first and the object second. Emotional design participates in the transfer of "interpersonal" values in the world of things, to induce a state of well-being and familiarity to the user. [Bolz, 1994]

The different ways in which designers treat things allows them to be inspired by the empathy for the emotional experiences of people who use with their product in their day to day life. From this idea emerges the concept that the user can and should be a key factor in the design process. [Sanders, Dandavate, 1996] This can take place in a context that generates the experience the consumer has with the product. It is necessary to plan in advance some scenarios of human - product interaction that involve all the senses and result in a pleasant experience which is intended to be repeated.

Not long ago, the emphasis was on the optimal functioning of the product and its ease of use. Now, these objectives began to give way to the pleasant experience that man derives from the product. This experience can simply mean a visual contact with the product or a complex interaction, but regardless of type, its sole purpose is to satisfy all human senses. However, the many challenges of research focused on the user's emotion, product personality and the user's contribution to the creation process led to this topic being vaguely and fragmentarily addressed. The few related studies of the last 20 years are sectoral approaches and do not fully address issues connected to the personality of products and their co-creation.

1. The role and importance of experience and emotion in design

Andrei Dumitrescu claims that the experience of design can be defined as a contact, even if only a visual one, with a product. According to him, the experience of a product falls into two broad categories: casual and projected experience. The user may have a casual experience when the creators only focus on product functionality and ergonomics, but the experience of the product (albeit ignored) exists, and it can be either felicitous or infelicitous. The projected experience generates a series of pleasant emotions such as satisfaction, pleasure or delight [Dumitrescu A., 2013].

In the past, designers devoted all their resources to make the product easy to use, ergonomically sound and eye-catching. In the last 30 years, they focused on positive experiences that the user can gain from interacting with the product. With new generations being captivated by the product's response to their reactions (even those of confusion), the consumer shows a general tendency towards surprise and amusement and seeks to relive this experience. This reaction has an important role in the purchase decision. At the foundation of this concept lies man's inclination to react to all things around him through emotions.

Another important aspect is the very wide variety of products nowadays, compared to the offer from 100 years ago, when the first products appeared. This forces designers to find new ways to differentiate their products from their competitors, focusing more on the emotional responses and experiences in the user-product relation, leaving functional benefits in the background [Diener, Lucas 2000].

Pieter Desmet argues that "skilled designers understand the strong appeal of emotions and have used their intuition and artistic skills to exploit this aspect" [Desmet, 2002]. For them, the design process that arouses increased interest on the user side comes from creating products that involve emotion in design, by bringing together two contradictory terms. As William Green says, design involves order and reason, while emotion brings irrationality and spontaneity. [Green, 2002]

Man's perception of his objects changes throughout time. If at first, it is more or less a necessity, as the years go by, the object gains emotional value, through the memories and emotions created around it. This feature cannot be given by a designer, it is a personal contribution that goes beyond the traits predefined by the creator. Norman reinforces this idea by stating that the objects in our environment represent much more than material possessions, they gain a value through the meaning they bring to our lives, becoming a symbol. [Norman, 2004].

The century we live in is constantly developing, consumer expectations increase day by day. Whether they are influenced by marketing strategies, trends or advertisements, the requirements for consumer products have changed. If until recently, designers and users appreciated the functionality, ease of use and attractiveness, now these qualities are taken for granted. Moreover, they have higher expectations from everyday products. The task of the designer is hampered by new standards, because the consumer doesn't only expect a product to perform all its functions correctly and quickly, but he also looks for a message to respond to.

The emotional response is the result of an interaction that takes place in a given context between an individual and a product. Donald Norman argues that the emotional aspect of the product can replace functional ones stating that "... there is also a strong emotional component of how products are designed and used, more critical to a product's success than its practical elements" [Norman, 2004] .

Desmet and Hekkert launch three key concepts designed to outline the process of triggering emotions, being represented by a series of stimuli that come from a product: concern and appreciation. [Desmet, Hekkert, 2002]. Unfortunately, analyzing these models we can identify an important element that is missing, namely, the designers' lack of preoccupation for the characteristics

of the object to which the subject will react. Chakrabarti and Gupta thus remark that “the subject is capable of a variety of responses and it is unlikely that those consistent patterns between them and objects will be found” [Chakrabarti, Gupta, 2007]. Psychologist Robert Plutchick has created a model that includes eight universally valid human emotions as follows: acceptance, anger, anticipation, disgust, joy, fear, sadness and surprise. [Plutchik, 1980] Based on these eight emotions and the three basic states of arousal established by Ekman, Chakrabarti and Gupta developed the “Emotional Response Model” - ERM, representing the characteristics of the object that are stimuli for the user. The subject's preferences trigger one or more emotions. They argue that "emotional traits provide the bridge between object traits and primary emotions." [referinta] The model of the two stipulates that a number of characteristics of the object have direct relationships with the emotional traits, that in turn have a specific relationship with the eight primary emotions, the evaluation process being facilitated by the structure of the model [Chakrabarti, Gupta, 2007].

The attachment for the product is defined as the power of the emotional connection experienced by man with a product, thus involving the existence of an emotional connection between a user and an object with a significance for him. [Schifferstein and Pelgrim 2004] Creating the emotional relationship in design is based on a series of moderate emotions of surprise, delight, satisfaction and pleasure, so that the user can decide what matters to him; there is no need to arouse high-intensity emotions that are experienced on the first contact with the product, but rather numerous small pleasures [Andrei Dumitrescu, 2013]. Due to the personal nature of the emotions, the user has complete freedom regarding their type and degree of intensity. There is no valid general relationship between the appearance of the product and the emotion it generates.

The experience can also be induced through advertising. The manufacturer simulates a possible situation in which the buyer lives a pleasant experience in relation to the presented product, which triggers an emotional relationship with it.

Fig.1. Hornbach's advertisement that induces emotion by simulating an experience [1]

Experience is equally important for designers who may have informative personal experiences that make it easier for them to understand current issues and feel greater empathy for the people who will be influenced by their decisions. The ability of designers to access buyers' experiences through a number of methods such as listening, observing and deducing customer wishes gives them the satisfaction of generating pleasant emotions [Sanders, Dandavate, 1999].

After building the sentimental relationship between man and product, the occurrence of several disruptive factors can decrease consumer satisfaction with the product, one of which is perceptual wear and tear. This happens after the purchase, when the person sees the product very often, thus the emotions that stirred him at the beginning have diminished now. The buyer compares the new

and fall into two main categories: negative emotions and positive emotions. The conclusions of the study conducted by Pieter Desmet is that that "there is no one-to-one correspondence between design and the emotion the product produces; it is not a mere emotion, but the meaning that the product has for the customer". [Desmet, 2002] However, many products manage to induce such strong emotions that some people end up loving them, and others deeply disliking them. It follows that different products will succeed in satisfying one type of people, while failing to do so for another type.

Numerous studies have shown that attractive products keep their function longer, because they are used with more care. The variety of emotions aroused by the product can fuse into a strong feeling of affection called attachment, which differs from the others by increasing in intensity over time. Attachment is defined by Mugge as "the strength of the emotional connection that the consumer experiences for a certain product" [Mugge, 2007]. An important advantage of this attachment is the lasting connection between man and product, which prevents him from giving up the product even when it breaks down or no longer fulfills its default functions. Belk states that when a person is attached to a product that belongs to him, it is very possible to treat it with care, postponing the replacement of the product by repairing it when it breaks down" [Belk, 1991].

Emotions help us perceive the environment beyond the rational elements, after we go through a physical perception through our senses. They are meant to create relationships based on how we feel around an object, being or person. Depending on the experience, the user tends to associate a product with memories, feelings and emotions. This information is difficult to identify and manage for each individual, and even more so for the masses. Nonetheless, its impact is difficult to neglect. Based on a series of general emotions encountered, researchers in the field have come to the conclusion that by managing and dosing the positive and negative emotions generated by products, the decision-making process can be influenced to a great extent. Thus, the buyer is impressed by products that stir positive emotions and kindle his interest through the complexity of its features put together in an attractive and intuitive way, while being discouraged by products that seem difficult to use and don't have an appealing appearance.

Products that stir emotions are sustainable, because they determine the user's attachment over time and his inability to give up the product easily, postponing its replacement by consecutive repairs or keeping it for years despite not being used anymore.

2. Definition and classification of the personality of the products

In the promotion and sale of products, three different practices are encountered: product personalization, customized products and product personality. The common goal of these is the adaptation of marketing strategies to the user's interest by improving his experience in relation to the product, but also include a number of elements which differentiate them.

Product personalization "aims to create individual communication with a single consumer or consumer segment". [5] The customized product differs from the product available on the market in that it is individually designed and has a unique character depending on the customer's need. Thus, it stands out from the standard product through shape, size, material and even components. Personalization uses basic demographic information, behavioral patterns, and buying preferences with respect to craft marketing experiences for a specific audience segment [5].

Customization is initiated by the user according to his preferences and claims to the product expressed directly through target information to meet his own needs, for which he is willing to pay

more [6]. Customization responds to a real need that the customer cannot give up or satisfy through the rest of the standard products on the market. Stan Davis provides a complete definition of the term "customization", described as "the process of delivering goods and services on the broad market that are modified to meet a specific customer need" [5].

The personality of products, unlike customization and personalization, involves characteristics of the human personality and attributes them to the products man comes into contact and identifies with. Thus, that product passes from the sphere of mass-produced goods, to that of a different product, enriched with human-like qualities and features, that the consumer can identify with and treat with care and attention.

The product can be defined as a lifeless object produced as a result of a design activity, with a predefined shape, functionality and appearance. The product can be devoid of personality in the first stage of its existence. Over time through contemplation and usage, it manages to create an emotional relationship with the user, thus gaining a personality similar to theirs.

Pascal Govers states that "Product personality is the profile of personality traits used by people to describe the specifics of the product and differentiate it from other products" [Govers, Mugge 2004]. Patrick Jordan considers that it represents a set of characteristics of the human personality used in the description of the specificity of a product [Jordan, 1997].

Bloom argues that personality is "a process that changes the functionality, interface, information content, or distinctiveness of a system to increase personal relevance to the individual" [Blom 2000].

Andrei Dumitrescu offers a more comprehensive definition stating that "the personality of the product is the set of strongly outlined features of the human personality used by man to distinguish the product from others and to justify the sentimental relationship with it" [Dumitrescu, 2013].

The congruence theory launched by Patrick Jordan in 1997 in the article "Product as Personalities" argued that the personality of future buyers is reflected in the design of new products that will achieve success [Jordan, 1997]. After launching this theory, many other authors have stated that the similarity between the personality of the products and that of the user have a beneficial contribution on the attachment that occurs between the buyer and the product. Among them are Govers and Mugge, who claim that the process of identifying a person with the personality of a product determines a positive influence in the perception and evaluation of the product [Govers, Mugge, 2004].

As Congruence Theory holds, people tend to make a comparison between the concept of self and the image of the product, preferring those products that have an image compatible with their self. They identify their own personality traits and look for products consistent with themselves [Aaker, 1999] and [Govers and Schoormans 2005].

The development of the relationship between user and product has a significant positive contribution to the success of the product and the extension of its life. The most precious objects of a man are not necessarily those with a significant material value, but the things that could be difficult to replace, to which he becomes strongly attached. It is not the material loss of the product that the owner regrets, but the emotional loss that he suffers as a result of investing time and developing feelings about the product [Schultz, Kleine and Kernan 1989]. An emotional relationship between a person and a product requires similarity of personality, so that they become more attached to products with a personality congruent to theirs, thus strengthening the theory of congruence and the concept developed by Schultz, Kleine și Kernan. [Ruth, Hendrik and Jan, 2005].

Dumitrescu classifies the relationship determined by the personality of the product into two broad categories: either perceived at the individual level or at the general level. At the individual level “the personality of the product is the result of the interaction of each user or contemplator with the respective product”, and at the general level “the personality of the product is generated by the creator and producer”. Thus, the personality of the product stands out when considering aspects related to the appearance and dynamics of the product [Dumitrescu, 2013].

Thus, the role of designers in designing products with personality becomes very important, because it can stimulate the attachment to the product and extend its life, provided it has a classic rather than a modern design.

One of the potential problems that arise in the design of products with personality is given by the fact that designers and users may perceive the meaning of products differently [Hsu et al., 2000].

Wishing to perfect the design process to make products with personality, many authors have developed a series of methods to analyze people's perception of the product personality in relation to their own personality. A convenient method is the statistical survey in which a number of subjects are asked to associate different personality traits with a predetermined product. If there is unity in the subjects' opinions, then the product is considered to have personality. Otherwise, if opinions are strikingly different, it results that the product does not have a clearly defined personality. Janet Finch believes that the surveys come with a series of formulation and coding constraints around the questions, which aim at predicting a series of actions based on the answers provided by the participant. The scenario method yields much better results provided the purpose is obtaining general images, and not details.

Patrick Jordan builds a rather controversial model considered difficult to understand and apply, it was based on the model from psychology called Briggs-Myers. It was considered difficult due to its cumbersome terminology, making it increasingly difficult for ordinary people who had no contact with the field of psychology to deepen it. [Jordan, 2002].

Andrei Dumitrescu proposes a model inspired by that of Jordan, based on an experiment that confirms the validity of the concept and the analyzed personality traits. The experiment achieved its goal, with the first objective being that of successfully testing and validating the concept of product personality and not evaluating the personality of the products used in the experiment [Dumitrescu, 2007]. This scale has the advantage that it can be used to compare different products belonging to the same category - necessary to evaluate a product in relation to its competitors, as well as products belonging to different categories. This comparison contributes to the creation of a database of reference products which have different personalities - a source of inspiration for designers.

The user tends to invest more time analyzing the product to determine how it works and pays more attention to it. Janlert and Stolterman argue that this interaction is greatly influenced by the appearance and personality of the product. [Janlert and Stolterman, 1997]

Product personality can help determine the user anticipate how to use and interact with the product. Intuitively, the user shows involvement in interacting carefully with a product that has a delicate, sensitive personality and design.

The user's preference is guided by his own personality which he involuntarily seeks in the things and objects around him to confirm his identity [Govers and Mugge, 2004; Govers and Schoormans, 2005]. The desire to express his personality and find it in the things around him is also supported by

Jordan: "it is about people's desire to assert their individual identity in an increasingly impersonal world" [Jordan, 2000].

Today's consumer is in a constant search for objects to help him stand out, and to satisfy his desire to be noticed and appreciated in a group. Sirgy states that possessions of personal identity are particularly important, as the use of products is a means of defining and symbolically expressing ones' identity [Sirgy 1982]. The user gains a state of comfort by the fact that his products help him to stand out in society. Sener and Kurtgozu explain that products can be useful in increasing our emotional communication, self-expression and other personal traits. [Sener and Kurtgozu, 2008]

It is known that some people invest impressive amounts of money in products that reflect their personality and help them improve their mood, shifting from a necessity to a means of expression.

Products become a tool through which people express their personality in front of others and the fastest way to stand out in a group. Objects enable them to connect more easily with new people and reconfirm their unique character in front of acquaintances, giving them confidence and balance. A product with personality stands out and is immediately identified by the user. It is also analyzed and labeled as appropriate or not to his own personality. The consumer's behavior changes in relation to a particular product, stirring his interest and causing him to handle it with more care. Products with personality are given a remarkable importance by the user. He comes to interact with them much more than with other products in the same category and that do not have a clearly defined personality.

3. Definition and classification of co-created products

At the foundation of the growth and continuous improvement of a company that wants to become a key player in the market lies the process of developing new products. Since a large volume of innovative ideas is required to properly meet the wishes and needs of customers with the possibility of reducing the huge costs of study and research, more and more companies choose to use the concept of co-creation. It is a process of designing a product or service in which the consumer is actively contributing with their own ideas and suggestions, bringing uniqueness and innovation to the product.

In an article, Jhon Czepiel suggests that the customer's input can lead to greater satisfaction [Czepiel, 1990]. Authors Kelley, Donnelly, and Skinner bring to the forefront a number of benefits that arise from customer involvement in the production process, namely: quality, employee performance and emotional responses [Kelley et al., 1990].

Consumption is an extremely symbolic cultural activity through which consumers give subjective meanings to products and services. Thus, from the cultural perspective of consumer studies, co-creation pushes companies to be responsible for setting the value of goods and services [Holbrook and O'Shaughnessy 1988, Belk et al.1989].

Michael Schrage points out that the ability of clients to provide valuable ideas and suggestions should not be neglected, but it cannot be considered a valence present in every client, implying a selection is needed [Schrage, 1995].

The co-creation process helps firms improve the growth and profitability of companies by enabling customers to play an active part [Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2000]. At the same time, it is acknowledged the importance of marketing a product based on the process of co-creating its value through the exchange of knowledge and opinions. This takes place between customers and partners who develop a service orientation based on common values creation. [Vargo and Lusch, 2004] In the process of collaboration, exchanges of opinions and arguments take place, unique experiences are

created and are meant to bring consumers and companies closer in a collaborative relationship, with benefits on both sides. [Prahalad and Ramaswamy, 2004]

Aric Rindfleisch and Matt O'Hern defined co-creation as a collaborative NPD (product development) activity in which customers actively and constantly contribute to the selection of content for a new product offer to be launched on the market. It consists of two stages: customers' contribution with ideas/suggestions, and the rigorous selection of the best input. Thus, customers become “essential participants in the product development process and in some cases, are able to create new products with little help from companies” [O'Hern and Rindfleisch, 2008]. The authors reinforce this definition by offering as examples successful computer applications such as Apache, Linux and Firefox, which are projects managed exclusively by communities organized by volunteer programmers.

Companies seek to surprise their consumers with a series of interactive challenges that enable customers to customize the products they purchase. For example, www.nike.com provides customers with a Nike By You page that allows them to customize their own shoes, choosing from a wide range of colors and details.

Fig.4.Example of products that can be customized by consumers[4]

For a healthy evolution of the product development process, two types of fundamental information are needed: 1-information about customer needs and 2-information about how these needs can be met [Thomke and von Hippel2002; von Hippel 2005]. Manufacturers have solid and accurate knowledge of how they can meet customer needs, investing and working constantly to do their best. A shortcoming of information about customer needs has steered large investments go into marketing research with the purpose of shedding more light in this area.

Von Hippel and his colleagues have found a way to deal with this imbalance between known and hard-to-obtain information, by providing customers some knowledge and tools to actively participate in product development [Thomke and von Hippel 2002; von Hippel 2005; von Hippel and Katz 2002].

Starting from the idea supported by Belk, Richins and Dawson, that material objects do not have the capacity to respond to intrinsic psychological needs. Psychologists in the field claim that only by

stimulating creativity these needs can be met [Csikszentmihalyi, 1996]. Thus, bringing customers in the product creation process gains more ground and is facilitated by the development of the Internet.

Contribution and selection are two key processes which underline co-creation and are presented by O'Hern and Rindfleisch. They give rise to a conceptual typology of four forms of co-creation. The contribution process trains the public to offer the company a series of ideas, while the selection process picks the most promising contribution. The four types of co-creation are: collaborating, tinkering, co-designing and submitting, which are delimited according to the control exercised by the company or the public over the two components of the co-creation process.

This classification of the co-creation process represents a real progress compared to the traditional approach, first in the way customers are viewed and treated, and secondly by the role they play. [O'Hern and Rindfleisch, 2008]

The co-creation process benefits both the consumer and the company that adopts such a process for its services. Thus, we can distinguish the collection, classification and analysis of consumer preferences in order to provide real-time information, as well as make them known to the merchant. Reviews are another source of useful information for both parties. Reviews are designed to provide honest opinions and information to prospective buyers, as well as a feedback to the company [Zwass, 2010].

4. Conclusions regarding the strategies studied

The concepts elaborated in this article represent an important starting point in terms of strengthening the relationship between user and product. This also brings to the table ideas like the user's emotion, the product's personality and the user's contribution in the creation process, with the benefits of discovering a fresh perspective on this topic. I believe that emotion in design is closely related to the user experience, leading to attachment and then nostalgia. Research has shown that the emotional product-consumer bond improves personal satisfaction and life quality. The personality of the product has a pertinent contribution in terms of the user's self-esteem, making him stand out from the crowds that use mass products. Thus, co-creation is the missing link in a complete strategy regarding the optimal product development process in which the customer brings his personal touch to a product that manufacturers are now so eager to bring forth. I consider that the studied concepts play a role in creating the best version of products for consumers and if combined, they can meet their goal better than independently.

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